

Discrete Chi-Square Method (DCM)

Manual Version 2

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1 Introduction

Version 1 of this manual was published in Jetsu (2020b, Appendix). All **Version 1** files were stored in **Zenodo database: doi 10.5281/zenodo.3661072**.

This manual is **Version 2**. All files, variables and other program code related items in this manual are printed in **magenta** colour. DCM has been applied in three papers

Jetsu (2020c, Paper I)

Jetsu (2020c, Paper II)

Jetsu (2020a, Paper III)

All **Version 2** files are available in Zenodo. The user should copy these files to the same directory.

2 DCM computer code

This manual gives the instructions for the application of our Discrete Chi-square Method program **dcm.py**. We also briefly describe our Fisher test program **fisher.py**.

2.1 Control file

The main idea is that the user **never edits** the **dcm.py** program, but **only executes** it with the **python dcm.py** command. The user edits **only the last right hand column** of the control file **dcm.dat**. One example of a control file **dcm.dat** is given in the end of this manual. The **dcm.py** program may stop working for these reasons:

1. Any **'='** character is removed from **dcm.dat**, or added to **dcm.dat**.
2. Any of the first column numbers **1, 2, 3, ..., 24** is changed in **dcm.dat**. The **dcm.py** program uses these numbers to identify the input values for the variables given in the third column of **dcm.dat**.
3. Values for variables **K1, K2, K3, nL, nS, Rounds, SimN** and **SimRounds** are not integers in **dcm.dat**.

Program **dcm.py** has three different modes. The **SimMany** and **RealData** values in **dcm.dat** determine these modes.

SimMany \neq 1	RealData = 1	Mode 1: dcm.py analyses one sample of <i>real</i> data of file1 .
SimMany \neq 1	RealData \neq 1	Mode 2: dcm.py creates and analyses one sample of <i>simulated</i> data.
SimMany = 1	Any RealData value	Mode 3: dcm.py creates and analyses many samples of <i>simulated</i> data.

Most users probably select Mode 1 for analysing the real data in their own file **file1**. This requires only the editing of lines 1-15 in **dcm.dat**. Their real data analysis results do not depend on the next lines 16-23 of **dcm.dat**. These variables beginning with the letters **Sim** are relevant only in the simulation Modes 2 and 3.

2.2 Control file variables

In this section, we use the same numbering of the control file `dcm.dat` variables as in this file itself. The users can easily find the description of each variable, because their numbers below are highlighted with yellow background. Our `dcm.dat` example file can be found in the end of this manual.

- 1** `Tag` is text written to the beginning of the names of all output figures and files. This parameter `Tag` allows the user to store the results of each particular `dcm.dat` analysis into figures and files having the chosen specific names. For our chosen `Tag = Dec2019` in `dcm.dat`, those output figures are

`Dec2019z.eps` (e.g. Paper I: Fig. 2, Paper II: Fig. 1 or Paper III: Fig. 2)
`Dec2019gsim.eps` (Only if `RealData` $\neq 1$ and `SimMany` $\neq 1$, or `SimMany` = 1)
`Dec2019gdet.eps` (e.g. Paper I: Fig. 3, Paper II: Fig. 2 or Paper III: Fig. 3)
`Dec2019fA.eps` (e.g. Paper I: Figs. 4, 7 and 10)
`Dec2019Many.eps` (e.g. Paper I: Fig. 11: Only if `SimMany` = 1)
`Dec2019Signals.eps` (e.g. Paper II: Fig. 3 or Paper III: Fig. 4)

The output files are

`Dec2019Params.dat` (Results in Paper I (e.g. Table 4), Paper II (e.g. Table 2)T or Paper III (Table A9)
`Dec2019Residuals.dat` (Residuals file)
`Dec2019Points.dat` (Points file)
`Dec2019Curves.dat` (Curves file)
`Dec2019AllBeta.dat` (Free parameter file)
`Dec2019ManyfA.dat` (Relative frequency error file: Only if `SimMany` = 1)

The contents of these output files are described later in this manual.

- 2** `RealData` is used to select the analysed data. Its value is relevant only in Modes 1 and 2 when `SimMany` $\neq 1$.

`RealData=1` activates the *Mode 1* of program `dcm.py`, where it analyses the real data given in file `file1`.

`RealData` $\neq 1$ activates the *Mode 2* of program `dcm.py`, where it creates simulated data, stores these data to a file and analyses these data. It also creates a figure of the simulation model and the simulated data. For the `Tag = Dec2019` in our `dcm.dat`, the name of the input data figure is `Dec2019gsim.eps`. The simulated and analysed data file is `Dec2019SimulatedData.dat`. The output figure is `Dec2019gdet.eps`. The user can test many problems encountered with real data by simulating data having the same time span $\Delta T = \text{SimDT}$, sample size $n^* = \text{SimN}$ and signal to noise ratio $\text{SN} = \text{SimSN}$ as the real data. For `SimT` $\neq 1$, the time points for the simulated data are the same as for the real data in `file1`. With our `Tag=Dec2019`, the comparison between simulated `Dec2019gsim.eps` and detected `Dec2019gdet.eps` figures reveals directly, if DCM succeeds.

- 3** `file1` is the name of the file containing the real data analysed in Mode 1 (`RealData` = 1 and `SimMany` $\neq 1$). Its format must be the same as e.g. in Paper I: Table 3 (`Testdata.dat`) or Paper II: Table 2 (`hjdAlgol.dat`).

- 4** `dummy` is the value for input and output which contains no information. We use `dummy=-99.999`.

None of the analysed real or simulated observations $Y = y_i$ should have the numerical value of `dummy`.

None of the model parameters should have the numerical value of `dummy`.

- 5** `K1` = $K_1 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ or 6 signals (Paper I: Eq. 1)
6 `K2` = $K_2 = 1$ or 2 signal order (Paper I: Eq. 1)
7 `K3` = $K_3 = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ or 6 order polynomial trend (Paper I: Eq. 1)
8 `nL` = $n_L =$ number of tested frequencies in long search
9 `nS` = $n_L =$ number of tested frequencies in short search
10 `c` = $c =$ width of short tested frequency interval (Paper I: Eq. 15)

- 11 TestStat** is used to select the test statistic $z = z$.
- If **TestStat=1**, z is computed from χ^2 (Eq. 10: data errors known).
- If **TestStat \neq 1**, z is computed from R (Eq. 11: data errors unknown).
- 12 PMIN** = P_{\min} = minimum period
- If **RealData=1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 1), **PMIN** is the minimum tested period for the real data in **file1**.
- If **RealData \neq 1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 2), or **SimMany = 1** (Mode 3), **PMIN** is the minimum value for the random periods of simulated model(-s), as well as the minimum of tested periods for the simulated data.
- 13 PMAX** = P_{\max} = maximum period
- If **RealData=1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 1), **PMAX** is the maximum tested period for the real data in **file1**.
- If **RealData \neq 1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 2) or **SimMany = 1** (Mode 3), **PMAX** is the maximum value for the random periods of simulated model(-s), as well as the maximum of tested periods for the simulated data.
- 14 Rounds** = number of bootstrap rounds
- 15 NonLinear** determines, if a non-linear model iteration is performed.
- If **NonLinear=1**, program **dcm.py** performs a nonlinear iteration from β_{initial} to β_{final} (Paper I: Eq. 18).
- If **NonLinear \neq 1**, program **dcm.py** does not perform a non-linear iteration, and only uses the β_{initial} value of Eq. 18 in Paper I. This alternative may cause error messages, because low n_L and n_S test grid values can give the same results during many bootstrap rounds.
- 16 SimT** determines the t_i^* time points of simulated data when **RealData \neq 1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 2), or **SimMany = 1** (Mode 3).
- If **SimT = 1**, these simulated t_i^* time points are drawn from the uniform random distribution (Paper I: Eq. 21).
- If **SimT \neq 1**, the t_i time points of real data in file **file1** are used as time points t_i^* in the simulations. In this alternative, the user can simulate data having same time points $t_i = T$ as the real data. The user can also adjust the sample size **SimN**, the signal to noise ratio **SimSN** and the time span **SimDT** in **dcm.dat** to the values of real data.
- 17 SimN** = n^* = number of simulated observations when **RealData \neq 1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 2), or **SimMany=1** (Mode 3).
- 18 SimSN** = SN = signal to noise ratio of simulated observations (Paper I: Eq. 22) when **RealData \neq 1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 2), or **SimMany=1** (Mode 3).
- 19 SimDT** = ΔT time span of simulated observations when **RealData \neq 1** and **SimMany \neq 1** (Mode 2), or **SimMany=1** (Mode 3).
- 20 SimMany** activates the *Mode 3* of **dcm.py**.
- If **SimMany \neq 1** and **RealData=1**, **dcm.py** analyses *one* real data sample (Mode 1).
- If **SimMany \neq 1** and **RealData \neq 1**, **dcm.py** creates and analyses *one* simulated data sample (Mode 2).
- If **SimMany = 1**, **dcm.py** creates and analyses *many*, **SimRounds**, simulated data samples (Mode 3). With our **Tag = Dec2019** the results are figure **Dec2019Many.eps** (e.g. Paper I: Fig. 11) and file **Dec2019AllBeta.dat**.
- 21 SimRounds** = Number of simulated data samples created and analysed when **SimMany = 1**.
- 22 SimDF** = f_{crit} (Paper I: Eq. 28, the transparent diamonds in Fig. 11) when **SimMany = 1**.
- 23 SimDA** = A_{crit} (Paper I: Eq. 29, the transparent circles in Fig. 11) when **SimMany = 1**.
- 24 PrintScreen** controls printing to screen in all Modes 1-3.
- PrintScreen = 1** results are printed to screen. This allows the user to follow from the screen how the computations proceed, like the periods simulated and/or detected, or the bootstrap rounds completed.
- PrintScreen \neq 1** prevents printing to screen. This may be needed, if **dcm.py** is executed in batch.

```

Give n ..... = 500
Give p1 ..... = 12
Give p2 ..... = 13
Give Chi1 or R1= 496.10
Give Chi2 or R2= 492.94
F .... = 3.115511015539487
Q_F ...= 0.0781768378157

```

Figure 1: Application example of `fisher.py`.

2.3 Analysis results file

The main results of the analysis are stored in the analysis results file. The same information is also printed to the screen, if `PrintScreen = 1`. One example of this file `Dec2019Params.dat` is given in the end of this manual. The contents of this file are summarized in Table 1.

2.4 Residuals file

The ϵ_i residuals of the model are stored into the residuals file, which is `Dec2019Residuals.dat` with our `Tag = Dec2019`. Columns 1-3 are $T = t_i$, `EPSILON` = $\epsilon_i = y_i - g_i$, `EY` = σ_i . The format is the same as in the real data file `file1`, i.e. the format of this residual file is immediately suitable for further `dcm.py` period analysis.

2.5 Points file

This file is `Dec2019Points.dat` with our `Tag = Dec2019`. This file was not produced in **Version 1**.

2.6 Curves file

With our `Tag = Dec2019` this file is `Dec2019Curves.dat` This file was not produced in **Version 1**.

2.7 Free parameter file

This free parameter file is `Dec2019AllBeta.dat` with our `Tag = Dec2019`. It contains 39 columns. The first two columns are `TEPOCH` = t_1 and `DELTAT` = ΔT . For the free parameters β_i , our `dcm.py` program uses the index values i given in Table 2. All columns having `dummy` values contain no β_i value. If these `dummy` columns are removed, the remaining i columns are the β_i free parameters specified in Table 2. If necessary, the user can derive all functions of the $g(t)$ model from these parameters $t_1, \Delta T$ and β_i by using Eqs. 1-5 from Paper I.

In Mode 1 (`SimMany \neq 1`, `RealData = 1`), the first line contains the parameters $t_1, \Delta T$ and β_i for the original data sample in `file1`. Other lines contain these parameters for the bootstrap data samples.

In Mode 2 (`SimMany \neq 1`, `RealData \neq 1`), the first line contains the $t_1, \Delta T$ and β_i parameters for the original simulated data sample. Other lines contain these parameters for the bootstrap data samples.

In Mode 3 (`SimMany = 1`, any `RealData` value), the 1st, 3rd, ... , $2 \times \text{SimRounds} - 1$ lines contain the simulated $t_1, \Delta T$ and β_i model parameters. Every next line, the 2nd, 4th, ... , $2 \times \text{SimRounds}$ lines, contain the respective detected model parameters.

2.8 Relative frequency error file

This file is produced only when `SimMany = 1` (Mode 3). With our `Tag = Dec2019`, its name is `Dec2019ManyfA.dat`. Its contents are also printed in the screen when `PrintScreen = 1`. This file gives the relative frequency errors (Paper I: Eq. 30). The results are given separately for all models, as well as for those models that *do not* fulfill criteria of Paper I Eqs. 28 and 29, like models not highlighted in Fig. 11 of Paper I.

We show examples of `dcm.dat` and `Dec2019Params.dat` files in the end of this manual.

2.9 Fisher test

In this section, we explain how our program `fisher.py` computes the F_χ and Q_F estimates (e.g. Paper I: Table 4 or Paper II: Table A2). Executing `python fisher.py` asks for the numerical input values for $n = n$, $p1 = p_1$, $p2 = p_2$, $Chi1 = \chi_1$ or $R1 = R_1$, and $Chi2 = \chi_2$ or $R1 = R_2$. If the pair χ_1 and χ_2 is used, the $F = F_\chi$ value is computed from Eq. 12 of Paper I. For the R_1 and R_2 pairs, the $F = F_R$ value is computed from Eq. 13 of Paper I. The program prints the F value and the $Q = Q_F$ value of Eq. 14 of Paper I. The results for comparing models 19 and 20 of Paper I are shown in Fig. 1.

2.10 Least squares fit subroutine

The numerical python least squares subroutine `optimize.leastsq` minimizes the sum of squares $\sum_{i=1}^n [(y_i - g_i)/\sigma_i]^2$. The χ^2 estimates for the linear models of denser tested frequency grids agree with the results for the non-linear model (Paper I: Eq 18). In the python `optimize.leastsq` subroutine, the parameter `ftol` measures the relative error in the above sum of squares. The parameter `xtol` measures the relative error in the desired approximate solution. We use `ftol=0.0001` and `xtol=0.0001` in `optimize.leastsq` of our non-linear least squares fit `NonLinearLSF`, because this should prevent the numerical non-linear iteration $\bar{\beta}_{\text{final}}$ (Paper I: Eq. 18) from wandering too far from the unambiguous initial $\bar{\beta}_{\text{initial}}$ estimate obtained from linear modelling.

Amplitude dispersion occurs already for the unambiguous linear models, *before* any non-linear modelling is made. The numerical `optimize.leastsq` subroutine has to utilize these unrealistic high amplitude $h_i(t)$ curves, because this is the only possible way to minimize χ^2 . These high amplitude curves, which nearly cancel each other, offer the only possible way to fit two or more curves having nearly the same frequencies. From the purely mathematical point of view, these amplitude dispersion models do not fail. They are just unrealistic. There just are no reasonable low amplitude solutions. However, we know for certain that these unrealistic models fail, because we know that model 19 is the correct solution.

The `optimize.leastsq` is not an analytical subroutine, because it does not require the model partial derivative formulas as its input. Here is room for development for those who are prepared to code these $\partial g(t)/\partial \beta_i$ partial derivatives. But even that analytical solution could not eliminate amplitude dispersion, because the continuous and stable $z_1(f_1), \dots, z_{K_1}(f_{K_1})$ periodograms already confirm that there simply are no realistic low amplitude $h_i(t)$ curve solutions (e.g. Paper I: Figs. 5 and 8).

2.11 Qualitative program code description

Here, we give a short qualitative description of the stages of `dcm.py`.

1. First, the *long* tested frequency interval $f_{\min} = P_{\max}^{-1}$ and $f_{\max} = P_{\min}^{-1}$ is fixed. We create the n_L evenly spaced tested frequencies f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{K_1} between f_{\min} and f_{\max} . Such grids are illustrated in Fig. ???. The j :th tested value of frequency f_i is denoted with f_{i,j_i} ($j_i = 1, 2, \dots, n_L$).
2. We create the one-dimensional vectors $F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{K_1}, Z$ for collecting the period search results from the K_1 -dimensional tested frequency space. These vectors are empty before the loop of tested frequencies begins.
3. All $f_{1,j_1} > f_{2,j_2} > \dots > f_{K_1,j_{K_1}}$ combinations are tested in a loop. For each combination,
 - (a) We compute the periodogram test statistic $z = z[f_{1,j_1}, f_{2,j_2}, \dots, f_{K_1,j_{K_1}}]$ (Paper I: Eq. 10 or 11).
 - (b) The tested frequency combination and the result for z are appended into the collection vectors

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{1,\text{old}} \leftarrow f_{1,j_1} &\Rightarrow F_{1,\text{new}} = [F_{1,\text{old}}, f_{1,j_1}] \\
 F_{2,\text{old}} \leftarrow f_{2,j_2} &\Rightarrow F_{2,\text{new}} = [F_{2,\text{old}}, f_{2,j_2}] \\
 &\dots \Rightarrow \dots \\
 F_{K_1,\text{old}} \leftarrow f_{K_1,j_{K_1}} &\Rightarrow F_{K_1,\text{new}} = [F_{K_1,\text{old}}, f_{K_1,j_{K_1}}] \\
 Z_{\text{old}} \leftarrow z &\Rightarrow Z_{\text{new}} = [Z_{\text{old}}, z]
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

4. After completing the test frequency loop, we find the index k of the Z minimum. The best frequency candidates are at $F_1[k] = f_{1,\text{mid}}, F_2[k] = f_{2,\text{mid}}, \dots, F_{K_1}[k] = f_{K_1,\text{mid}}$ of Eq. 15 of Paper I (Fig. 1: diamonds).
5. We fix the *short* denser tested frequency grids (Paper I: Eq. 15), which are centered at $F_1[k], F_2[k], \dots, F_{K_1}[k]$. The more accurate best frequency values are determined by using these dense grids of n_S tested frequencies.
6. The bootstrap is used to solve the errors for model parameters within the *short* tested frequency intervals.

Table 1: Parameters of result file.

n, T1, DT	$n, t_1, \Delta T$	number of observations, first observing time, time span
my, sy, SN	m_y, s_y, SN	mean, standard deviation and signal to noise ratio of observations
K1, K2, K3	K_1, K_2, K_3	number of signals, signal order and polynomial trend order
p	p	number of free parameters
PMIN, PMAX	P_{\min}, P_{\max}	minimum and maximum tested period
nL, nS	n_L, n_S	number of tested frequencies in long and short search
CHI2, R	χ^2, R	chi-square and sum of squared residuals of the best model
F1, P1, A1, T1MIN1, T1MIN2, T1MAX1, T1MAX2	$h_1(t)$	parameters $f_1, P_1, A_1, t_{1,\min,1}, t_{1,\min,2}, t_{1,\max,1}, t_{1,\max,2}$
F2, P2, A2, T2MIN1, T2MIN2, T2MAX1, T2MAX2	$h_2(t)$	parameters $f_2, P_2, A_2, t_{2,\min,1}, t_{2,\min,2}, t_{2,\max,1}, t_{2,\max,2}$
F3, P3, A3, T3MIN1, T3MIN2, T3MAX1, T3MAX2	$h_3(t)$	parameters $f_3, P_3, A_3, t_{3,\min,1}, t_{3,\min,2}, t_{3,\max,1}, t_{3,\max,2}$
BETA [i]	$\bar{\beta}$	all free parameter values

The tested frequency combination $\bar{\beta}_I = [f_{1,j_1}, f_{2,j_2}, \dots, f_{K_1,j_{K_1}}]$ is swapped before stage 3a. We write the next tested frequencies into file **ALLF.dat** with subroutine **WriteALLF**. Subroutine **ReadALLF** reads these frequencies within another subroutine **LinearModel**. Hence, we do not have to rewrite the model equations for every new tested $\bar{\beta}_I = [f_{1,j_1}, f_{2,j_2}, \dots, f_{K_1,j_{K_1}}]$ combination. In stage 3b, the results from the K_1 -dimensional frequency grid space are projected into the one-dimensional collection vectors of Eq. 1.

We emphasize that although there may be coding errors in our **dcm.py** program. Ours is just one possible DCM application code. More talented coders can certainly improve our code.

3 Revisions

The main improvements in the **Version 2** of **dcm.py** code are explained in here.

3.1 Corrected bugs

1. If **TestStat** $\neq 1$, the DCM test statistic is the sum of squared residuals R . In **Version 1**, the linear least squares fit **LinearLSF** and the nonlinear least squares fit **NonLinearLSF** used weights computed from the errors of data. The correct approach would have been to use equal weights, because R assumes unknown weights. In **Version 2**, we use the mean of all σ_i for all observation errors in performing these least squares fits when **TestStat** $\neq 1$. This makes both of these fits non-weighted. This did not mislead our analysis in Paper I, because we analysed weighted data with known errors.
2. In **Version 1**, the tested frequencies of the short search could be negative in some cases when the long search interval was already close to zero frequency. This is no longer possible in **Version 2**, where we test only positive frequencies. This did not mislead our analysis in Paper I, because we did not use negative frequencies.
3. In **Version 1**, we subtracted the first time point **TO** = t_0 from all time points before modelling. In our figures, we never added it back. This is corrected in **Version 2**. Note that this was only a graphical bug that did not mislead the numerical results.

3.2 Improvements

1. **Version 2** produces a plot of each signal (e.g. Paper II: Fig. 3). We plot each $h_j(t_i)$ signal, and the values

$$y_{i,j} = y_i - [g(t_i) - h_j(t_i)]$$

For **Tag=Dec2019**, this figure is **Dec2019Signals.eps**

2. **Version 2** produces two new files. The first file **Dec2019Points.dat** contains columns

$$t_i \quad y_i \quad \sigma_i \quad g(t_i) \quad h_1(t_i) \quad h_2(t_i) \quad h_3(t_i) \quad h_3(t_i) \quad h_5(t_i) \quad h_6(t_i) \quad p(t_i)$$
 The second file **Dec2019Curves.dat** contains 5000 time points t_j evenly spaced between t_1 and t_n . The other columns can be used to reproduce of the continuous signal curves (e.g. Paper II: Fig. 3). The columns are

$$t_j \quad g(t_j) \quad h_1(t_j) \quad h_2(t_j) \quad h_3(t_j) \quad h_3(t) \quad h_5(t) \quad h_6(t_j) \quad p(t_j)$$

3. The program collects notes of problematic cases. For `Tag=Dec2019`, these notes are collected to file `Dec2019Notes.dat`. The contents of this file are also printed to screen, if `PrintScreen = 1`.
 - (a) A note is made, if the best period in the long or the short search is at the end or the beginning of the tested period interval. For example, `Long search: 1 period at edge` means that the result for best f_1 value is at the edge of tested period interval. This type of problems can be solved by adjusting `PMIN`, `PMAX`, `nL` or `nS`. This problem must be addressed, is this type of note is also present in the short search.
 - (b) “Intersecting frequencies” can not always be easily seen in the figures. These cases are now collected to notes like `1 and 2 frequencies intersect`.
4. We mark the periodogram minima with open diamonds (e.g. Paper II: Fig. 1). There are also minor graphical modifications that do not need to mentioned at all.

4 Reproducing our results

Here, we explain how the users can reproduce our main results, as well as practice the use of our CDM program `dcm.py`. After reproducing our results, the users can also be more confident about results for their own data.

4.1 Paper II (Jetsu, 2020a)

We add the letter `A` to the beginning of Paper II control files. This ensures that the control files of two papers do not get mixed. The whole period analysis in Table 2 of Paper II can be made with only eight Linux-commands

```
cp Ahjd14R112s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
cp Ahjd14R212s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
cp Ahjd14R312s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
cp Ahjd14R412s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
```

The rest of the results can be obtained with `fisher.py`.

4.2 Paper III (Jetsu, 2020c)

The name of each particular control file is given in all tables of Paper III. For example, the two linux commands

```
cp hjd14R111s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
```

procude the results of model M=1 in Table A7. Note that the analysis must proceed in correct order. For example the commands

```
cp hjd14R412s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
```

produce the results for M=4 in Table A9, including the file `hjd14R412sResiduals.dat`. This file is needed before executing the commands

```
cp hjd58R110s.dat dcm.dat
python dcm.py
```

which produce the results for model M=5 in Table A9.

Finally, all Fisher-test results in every table can be obtained with `fisher.py`.

References

- Jetsu, L. 2020a, ApJL (submitted)
- . 2020b, The Open Journal of Astrophysics, 3, 20
- . 2020c, JAAVSO (submitted)

Table 2: Programming indexes i for free parameters β_i . These indexes are given separately for $\bar{\beta}_I$ and $\bar{\beta}_{II}$. Columns “L” and “N” denote Linear and Non-linear models for given K_1 and K_2 combinations.

$\bar{\beta}_I$ free parameters																								
One period				Two periods				Three periods				Four periods				Five periods				Six periods				
$K_1 = 1$		$K_1 = 1$		$K_1 = 2$		$K_1 = 2$		$K_1 = 3$		$K_1 = 3$		$K_1 = 4$		$K_1 = 4$		$K_1 = 5$		$K_1 = 5$		$K_1 = 6$		$K_1 = 6$		
$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		
L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	
f_1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1
f_2	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	-	2
f_3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	3	-	3	-	3	-	3	-	3	-	3	-	3
f_4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	4	-	4	-	4	-	4	-	4
f_5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	5	-	5	-	5	
f_6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	6	
$\bar{\beta}_{II}$ free parameters																								
One period				Two periods				Three periods				Four periods				Five periods				Six periods				
$K_1 = 1$		$K_1 = 1$		$K_1 = 2$		$K_1 = 2$		$K_1 = 3$		$K_1 = 3$		$K_1 = 4$		$K_1 = 4$		$K_1 = 5$		$K_1 = 5$		$K_1 = 6$		$K_1 = 6$		
$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		$K_2 = 1$		$K_2 = 2$		
L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	L	N	
$B_{1,1}$	1	2	1	2	1	3	1	3	1	4	1	4	1	5	1	5	1	6	1	6	1	7	1	7
$C_{1,1}$	2	3	2	3	2	4	2	4	2	5	2	5	2	6	2	6	2	7	2	7	2	8	2	8
$B_{1,2}$	-	-	3	4	-	-	3	5	-	-	3	6	-	-	3	7	-	-	3	8	-	-	3	9
$C_{1,2}$	-	-	4	5	-	-	4	6	-	-	4	7	-	-	4	8	-	-	4	9	-	-	4	10
$B_{2,1}$	-	-	-	-	3	5	5	7	3	6	5	8	3	7	5	9	3	8	5	10	3	9	5	11
$C_{2,1}$	-	-	-	-	4	6	6	8	4	7	6	9	4	8	6	10	4	9	6	11	4	10	6	12
$B_{2,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	9	-	-	7	10	-	-	7	11	-	-	7	12	-	-	7	13
$C_{2,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	10	-	-	8	11	-	-	8	12	-	-	8	13	-	-	8	14
$B_{3,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	8	9	12	5	9	9	13	5	10	9	14	5	11	9	15
$C_{3,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	9	10	13	6	10	10	14	6	11	10	15	6	12	10	16
$B_{3,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	14	-	-	11	15	-	-	11	16	-	-	11	17
$C_{3,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	15	-	-	12	16	-	-	12	17	-	-	12	18
$B_{4,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	11	13	17	7	12	13	18	7	13	13	19
$C_{4,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	12	14	18	8	13	14	19	8	14	14	20
$B_{4,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	19	-	-	15	20	-	-	15	21
$C_{4,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	20	-	-	16	21	-	-	16	22
$B_{5,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	14	17	22	9	15	17	23
$C_{5,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	15	18	23	10	16	18	24
$B_{5,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	19	24	-	-	19	25
$C_{5,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	25	-	-	20	26
$B_{6,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	17	21	27
$C_{6,1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	18	22	28
$B_{6,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	23	29
$C_{6,2}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	24	30
M_0	3	4	5	6	5	7	9	11	7	10	13	16	9	13	17	21	11	16	21	26	13	19	25	31
M_1	4	5	6	7	6	8	10	12	8	11	14	17	10	14	18	22	12	17	22	27	14	20	26	32
M_2	5	6	7	8	7	9	11	13	9	12	15	18	11	15	19	23	13	18	23	28	15	21	27	33
M_3	6	7	8	9	8	10	12	14	10	13	16	19	12	16	20	24	14	19	24	29	16	22	28	34
M_4	7	8	9	10	9	11	13	15	11	14	17	20	13	17	21	25	15	20	25	30	17	23	29	35
M_5	8	9	10	11	10	12	14	16	12	15	18	21	14	18	22	26	16	21	26	31	18	24	30	36
M_6	9	10	11	12	11	13	15	17	13	16	19	22	15	19	23	27	17	22	27	32	19	25	31	37

Contents of `dcm.dat`

```

1 = Tag           = Dec2019
2 = RealData     = 1
3 = file1       = TestData.dat
4 = dummy       = -99.999
5 = K1          = 3
6 = K2          = 1
7 = K3          = 2
8 = nL          = 60
9 = nS          = 30
10 = c          = 0.20
11 = TestStat   = 1
12 = PMIN       = 1.0
13 = PMAX       = 2.0
14 = Rounds     = 30
15 = NonLinear  = 1
16 = SimT       = 1
17 = SimN       = 500
18 = SimSN      = 100
19 = SimDT      = 4.0
20 = SimMany    = 0
21 = SimRounds  = 3
22 = SimDF      = 0.05
23 = SimDA      = 0.50
24 = PrintScreen = 1.0

```

Contents of `Dec2019Params.dat`

```

n 500
T1 1.9547820000e-03
DT 3.9958894740e+00
my -1.2567031722e+00
sy 2.2066570834e+00
sigma 2.6888315618e-02
SN 4.6424393691e+02
K1 3
K2 1
K3 2
p 12
PMIN 1.0000000000e+00
PMAX 2.0000000000e+00
nL 60
nS 40
CHI2 4.9309212497e+02 gives ZMIN 9.9306809934e-01
R 5.6396874104e-01 gives ZMIN 3.3584780513e-02
.....
F1 9.0911731600e-01 +/- 1.2735271893e-03
P1 1.0999680486e+00 +/- 1.5420877320e-03
A1 9.0070629802e-01 +/- 1.5914601221e-02 SN 67.00
T1MIN1 3.2534538828e-01 +/- 1.1847765288e-03
T1MIN2 ... +/- ...
T1MAX1 8.7532941256e-01 +/- 5.3225925012e-04
T1MAX2 ... +/- ...
.....
F2 7.1406875500e-01 +/- 6.6356730224e-03
P2 1.4004253694e+00 +/- 1.3149673657e-02
A2 1.0016254884e+00 +/- 3.2552250810e-02 SN 74.50
T2MIN1 4.9569244560e-02 +/- 1.4268052938e-02
T2MIN2 ... +/- ...
T2MAX1 7.4978192926e-01 +/- 7.7035844527e-03
T2MAX2 ... +/- ...
.....
F3 5.2638452700e-01 +/- 4.0181847831e-03
P3 1.8997518899e+00 +/- 1.4379538506e-02
A3 1.1011510476e+00 +/- 4.6003971393e-02 SN 81.91
T3MIN1 4.2559945346e-01 +/- 9.8085696951e-03
T3MIN2 ... +/- ...
T3MAX1 1.3754753984e+00 +/- 2.6765025920e-03
T3MAX2 ... +/- ...
.....
i BETA[i]
1 F1 9.09117e-01 1.27353e-03
2 F2 7.14069e-01 6.63567e-03
3 F3 5.26385e-01 4.01818e-03
4 B11 1.22518e-01 2.30736e-03
5 C11 -4.33368e-01 8.68889e-03
6 B21 -4.89585e-01 2.14509e-02
7 C21 -1.05456e-01 3.02140e-02
8 B31 -9.37527e-02 2.12900e-02
9 C31 -5.42535e-01 2.62038e-02
10 M0 1.79955e+00 2.20915e-03
11 M1 -1.49889e+00 2.81791e-03
12 M2 -1.20073e+00 1.33342e-03

```